

Equality, Justice and Harmony

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STUDY ON MEN

LEGALISING MISANDRY TO EMPOWER WOMEN

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In today's world there is a tendency in our society to brand every man as a villain and every woman as a victim. Because of the rise in feminism and of the supporters of feminism, there has also been an increase in the numbers of white knights who has share in name, fame and money in feminist's victory. When the whole of society is against men, then it is very easy to brand men as sadists, child-molesters, pedophiles, genital mutilators, gang rapists etc.

In addition to what society is thinking and supporting, even the legal systems of most countries are aligned with Feminists.

In India, Article 20 is one of the pillars of fundamental rights guaranteed by the Constitution. It mainly deals with the protection of certain rights in cases of conviction for offences. When individuals or corporations are accused of crimes, then the provisions of Article 20 safeguard their rights.

Our constitution is based on the fundamental principle of "**Let Hundreds of Guilty Persons Go Unpunished, But Never Punish an Innocent Person**" Right to obtain fair representation in criminal procedures is a facet of the Right to Equality (Article 14)

Article 20 mandates that "**no person shall be convicted of any offence except for violation of a law in force at the time of the commission of the act charged as an offence, nor be subjected to a penalty greater than that which might have been inflicted under the law in force at the time of the commission of the offence**". Thus, the Accused is given fair and equal treatment on par with other citizens. Also, by judicial pronouncements, a wider ambit has been imparted to the Right to life and liberty and thus the Accused are required to be treated humanely in jails fulfilling the reformatory approach (Article 21). Article 22 mandates that no person shall be detained in custody without being informed, as soon as may be, of the grounds for such arrest; nor shall he be denied the right to consult and to be defended by a legal practitioner of his choice. The exception to the right is that it is not

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to be applied in case of an alien. Thereby, these rights under the Constitution are inherent rights and cannot be altered or changed.

In today's world, and specially in India; even when a case is still under investigation, the charge sheet not being filed and trial yet to begin with the Court yet to hear the Accused and the Prosecution and it remaining to be proved that the Accused is guilty, the Accused men are instantly branded as criminals by society, the legal system and the government preventing them from leading normal lives. As soon as women file any false case on men, the men are treated as antisocial elements and worse than terrorists. Their passports are seized, they are dismissed from their jobs, and they are prevented from travelling, all of which is enough to drive them to - and which in innumerable cases has led them to commit - suicide. The legal system treats them as **"Guilty until proven Innocent"** when all over the world it is Innocent till proven Guilty - this is the beauty of the Indian Legal System.

Advertising companies produce misandrist ADs that promote men being slapped by women, and which proclaim that the Girl is always right while the Boy is always wrong, that Women perform better than Men etc.

The Indian Government has created more than 50 schemes, reservation and funds meant exclusively only for the girl child and women but none at all for boys and men; there is a separate government ministry to only look after the interests of and to take care of women but there is none for men.

Most tellingly, at the United Nations, there is an **Un_Women** but no **UN_Men**.

Exposing Feminist agenda, vested interests, ill-deeds is treated as misogyny and such men are branded as women haters - as bad as Jack the Ripper. Some radical feminists even claim men are biologically inferior and inherently immoral. At the same time feminists promote their agenda by claiming themselves to be victims of patriarchal society and that they are weaker sex and oppressed by men; when it comes to matters of alimony, they claim that men make more money and that women are financially oppressed by men. So

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if as per them, men are inferior then how is it that they also claim that Men earn more money and own more assets?

Some Radical Feminists have in fact demanded Bachelor Tax be imposed on men who go their own way (MGTOW) and such men are described as anti-feminist and misogynist.

There was an article by UN Women (Twitter Handle: [@UN_Women](#)) with the heading **SOCIAL MEDIA MONITORING ON COVID-19 AND MISOGYNY IN ASIA AND THE PACIFIC** which has deliberately ignored all facts, figures and statistics collected and published by Government bodies and reputed organizations like NCRB - this radical feminist organization then went on to demand legal action and even more laws favoring women.

Some of the one-sided and biased recommendations are as follows.

As we celebrate the 20th anniversary of UN Security Council resolution 1325, we must also recognize that trends in the digital sphere have also undermined the very goals the Women, Peace and Security (WPS) agenda has sought to realize. This absence of security online hinders women's participation in the public sphere, governance and leadership roles, especially in the context of conflict prevention and in promoting social cohesion. Should this deficiency in women's engagement online in the region continue, the status quo is sure to be preserved, maintaining influence in the hands of the very powerful few, and stalling the transformative change that the WPS framework envisages. Thus, women's digital engagement and use of technologies are at a critical juncture with regards to the achievement of the WPS agenda. The following recommendations are targeted towards governments, development organizations and researchers in South and South-East Asia:

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1. Build the capacity of women in South and South-East Asia to identify, report and block hateful content, as well as for men and women on social media literacy and countering disinformation as the region witnesses increased volumes of misogyny and hate speech targeting women online, it is crucial that women users of social media are aware of how to protect themselves. Likewise, misogynist tweets and Facebook posts, especially in South Asia, are often based on news stories that are fake or taken out of context. This suggests that increased levels of social media literacy among both men and women would limit the efficacy of such posts in spreading their hateful agendas.

2. Pass legislation that criminalizes cyber harassment and cyber stalking Although States often have existing laws that prohibit stalking or harassment, these laws are sometimes inadequate to criminalize harms that happen online. Thus, specific laws to address cyber harassment and stalking can close this gap.

3. Monitor and remove misogynist content on social media platforms Social media companies have increasingly sought to regulate what content is publishable on their platforms, banning everything from election misinformation to photos depicting violence. However, no ban against misogyny, particularly violent misogyny has yet been introduced, which affects the safety and free speech of women users.

4. Produce and disseminate gender empowerment-themed content targeted at men The overwhelming majority of COVID-19-related misogynistic content is posted by male users, across platforms and countries. One way to tackle the root of these gender biases and prejudices is by developing localized and engaging counter-narrative content. This could entail enlisting the participation and support of local

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entertainers and influencers who have large followings and using content styles and formats that men are likely to engage with.

5. Research the scope and impact of online misogyny on closed social networks such as WhatsApp, private Facebook groups, and Telegram Investigating the prevalence of online misogyny on closed platforms and private groups would allow a comprehensive understanding of the full extent of online misogyny in South and South- East Asia. Closed social networks can provide greater anonymity, allowing for greater incitement to violence and hatred with impunity.

6. Research potential links between nationalism and misogyny among social media users in Asia The suggested intersectionality between nationalism and misogyny among social media users outlined in this brief merit further investigation and validation. In an age of growing nationalism across the region, examining potential linkages between nationalism and misogyny among online users would provide relevant insights into the root causes and consequences of online misogyny.

THIS CLEARLY SHOWS RADICAL FEMINIST MENTALITY AND REVEALS THEIR FEAR OF LOSING GROUND WHEN THEIR FALSEHOODS ARE EXPOSED - THEIR INTENTION IS TO SILENCE THE TRUTH REGARDING FAKE FEMINISM BY MISREPRESENTING SUCH TRUTHS AS MISOGYNY WHILE PRETENDING TO BE INNOCENT VICTIMS AND ALSO DEMANDING LEGAL ACTION FOR EXPOSING THEIR BLATANT LIES.

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SOUTH AFRICA:

South Africa's government has introduced three Bills in Parliament to curb gender-based violence.

President Cyril Ramaphosa has termed them as the "*most far-reaching legislative overhaul in the fight against gender-based violence and femicide*".

The proposed changes seek - among other things - to create a new offence of sexual intimidation, to allow names of sex offenders to be publicly available and to make it more difficult to grant bail to perpetrators of violence against women.

They also impose new obligations on police officers, prosecutors and courts in the handling of cases.

In Europe if law makers attempt to pass any laws to check abuse and misuse of the legal system and to punish women who file false rape cases against men, mass media immediately opposes the same by asking "***Are Europe's rape laws letting women down?***" - anyone can easily research this by searching online for more details.

This clearly shows that Feminists do not want women's complaints to be checked, scrutinized and verified properly, they want the Police/Legal Authority to accept any complaint made by a woman exactly as narrated by her. They want that the Authorities should not cross-check with the Accused man for his version. The reason is that most times Rape cases are in fact incidents of consensual sex, but when things go wrong or not as per what the woman wants, then such women falsely claim Rape.

In most countries only women have the option to report Domestic Violence since only women are considered as Victims and there is no system whatsoever for men to report Domestic Violence committed against themselves. Equality and equal protection of laws is only in the Law books and is not seen in actual practice. We have collected hundreds of cases of murders of husbands at the hands of their wives, (**CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN**

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- <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>) in the earlier six months of the pandemic. Not even one such murder made national headlines, nor has the foreign media highlighted - or made any documentaries on - the same. This clearly shows strong media bias against Men.

At the same time we have reported suicides by men because of marital discord (**MEN'S LIVES MATTERS - SUICIDES BY MEN - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH** - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4649599>), these also have not made any national headlines nor has any foreign media highlighted the same - and why? - because there is a systematic plan of radical Feminists to silence the truth.

Indian Society, Spouse and System Push Men to take drastic steps finally leading them to end their own precious lives. Feminist mafia, prejudiced Indian society, one-sided media, negative bias from birth, and gynocentric, short-sighted Government Policies that completely neglect Indian men are the main reasons which are responsible for cutting short Men's lives.

Government of India is over enthusiastic to buy into the worldwide feminist ideology. But feminism disguised as women's empowerment is causing severe damage to the unifying fabric of cultural, family and spiritual values that define this nation. The core mindset of the Government is misandrist which is clearly visible in the lack of support and absence of any help to Men in distress. Men are left out in the cold with no Law to take recourse to when victimized and are therefore more commonly resorting to suicide. The rate of Men's suicide in India is alarming with male deaths from suicides being nearly double that of females thanks to the rising numbers of fake cases, ill treatment by society and total neglect by the Government.

Worldwide around 800,000 people die due to suicide yearly, that's one person every 40 seconds. Of these 1,39,123 (18%) are residents of India. 70% of suicides are by men and is mostly due to depression because of marital discord, which is responsible for their deaths. The overall male to female ratio of suicide victims for the year 2019 was 70.2: 29.8, which is more as compared to the year 2018 (68.5: 31.5). Globally, the suicide rate

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for men is twice than of women. All of these statistics are not only deliberately concealed but also suppressed by chauvinistic feminist organizations like UN_Women.

All the above statistics show why men are committing suicide. Most of the suicides are because of family problems, threats from wives to file fake cases, financial commitment towards the family, one sided laws, Reservation and Schemes meant only for females, zero support from government, zero protection from current laws against false accusations and fake cases. Men are abused, vilified, exploited and are expected to suffer in silence while women on the other hand are treasured, protected and pampered. Every country in the world, and their governments are busy pushing agendas for women's empowerment making special provisions for women's reservations / schemes / funding and enacting gender biased laws in favour of women without any safe guards against false cases. More MEN are suffering at the hands of an abusive female – wife / girlfriend / live-in partner which leads to depression and suicide. Yet strangely enough, hardly any studies have ever been conducted to research the psychological trauma that men have to face on a daily basis for years together. Truly men today are under attack from all sides and the day is not far off when to be born as a male will be considered the biggest curse and liability. Every aspect of the above mentioned details proves an unmistakable bias and discrimination against the male child even before birth. Today's generation in fact opts for the female child over the male child (gender selection) as there are many schemes and reservation meant only for the girl child (eg: BETI BACHAO / SAVE THE GIRL CHILD) and not a single Reservation/Quota system in Education, jobs, commuting etc. for the male child. Thus there is **SYSTEMIC DISCRIMINATION** against Men and in favour of WOMEN. Being born as a MAN is more of a SIN and really a CURSE in today's World, especially in India.

Government policies, media propaganda and societal attitudes are doing their very best to silence the truth of men's misery and problems by highlighting only a few crimes of men while shielding major crimes committed by women, by openly threatening legal proceeding against any attempts to expose the truth terming the same as misogyny, and by making laws to justify crimes committed by women portraying these as done in self-

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defense - murder of a Man is justified by (falsely) claiming that the Woman was saving herself from violence. These are the goals that radical feminists are planning to achieve.

ALL OF THIS POINTS TO ONE AND ONLY ONE INTENTION:

TO CONTROL AND DOMINATE MEN, TO DESTROY ANY HOPE OF LIVING A HAPPY FAMILY LIFE AND TO MAKE MEN ABSOLUTE SLAVES OF WOMEN

This is the ultimate aim of Extremist, Sadistic, Radical Feminists.

What feminists are afraid most of is losing all the years of their malicious efforts in which men - out of good faith - have mistakenly assisted. Most of the Laws, Rules, Perks and money granted were by and from men. Men made laws for women, Men granted them the right to vote, Men have generously promoted and supported them but in return these sadist feminists misused and manipulated their privileges - this has given birth to the Men's Rights Movement and a new dimension of the backlash against women's fake anti-violence advocacy is the rise of Indian Men's Rights Organizations formed to promote reversal of the bias against men. Feminists realize this will ultimately abolish all the free meal-tickets that they have been enjoying all these years, and have therefore falsely termed as misogyny the true facts disseminated by such men's rights groups viz. of women wreaking destruction on the Indian family system through their misuse of "gender-biased" laws. These feminists can hide the truth for some time but they can never erase it. The feminist's organizations do not want to admit that they are in fact digging the grave of their extremist ideology by distorting reality that will ultimately jeopardize their malicious advocacy efforts, and will end the unjustified socio-legal benefits that they are currently enjoying. This is the ultimate fear of feminists who are trying their level best to silence the voices of Men protesting the bias against and injustice meted to themselves.

Feminists should realize that in the modern internet age their false and misguided propaganda will no longer bear any fruit as an ever increasing number of people begin to realize that it is in fact Men who today are discriminated against right from birth, that it

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is Men who need to be protected against Domestic Violence committed by Women and that it is Men who are treated as second class citizens in many countries around the world with India regrettably topping the list. As more and more people - not only Men but also other Women and children - are falsely accused and unjustly convicted due to one-sided women-centric laws, the numbers of such Men's Rights Activists is only bound to increase and Governments will be forced to take notice of the falsehoods and hypocrisy of extremist feminist organizations like UN_Women who should keep in mind the words of Abraham Lincoln: "You can fool all the people some of the time and some of the people all the time, but you cannot fool all the people all the time".

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ORIGINAL SOURCE: <https://mynation.net/voice/legalising-misandry/>

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